

SACRALIZATION OF LUMBAR VERTEBRAE: PREVALENCE ACCORDING TO CASTELLY CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract:

Background: The study aimed to assess variations in the lumbar transverse process and evaluate the types of Castellvi classification using Computed Tomography (CT) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). These imaging modalities provide detailed visualization of both bone and soft tissues, assisting in identifying anatomical variants and guiding pre-operative planning to minimize complications.

Methods: A retrospective study was conducted at A.J. Hospital and Research Centre, Mangalore, from September 2023 to June 2024, involving 874 patients aged 20–80 years. CT scans were performed using a Siemens Somatom go. Top Dual Energy 128-slice scanner, and MRI scans with a MAGNETOM AVANTO 1.5T system. The L5 transverse processes were analysed for variations according to the Castellvi classification (Types I–IV and subtypes).

Results: Among 874 individuals (502 males and 372 females), 16.5% showed transverse sacralization of the lumbosacral vertebrae. Castellvi Type IIa was the most common variant (5.4%). Normal variants (Type I) accounted for 22.7%, with Type Ia most frequent (11.8%). Normal anatomy was observed in 60.8% of cases.

Conclusion: CT and MRI play a vital role in detecting anatomical variations of the lumbar transverse process and classifying them using Castellvi types. Recognizing these variants is essential for accurate vertebral level identification and surgical planning to reduce intraoperative complications.

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INTRODUCTION:

The purpose of the study was to assess the variation in lumbar vertebra and to evaluate the types of Castellvi classification in transverse process and to determine the common variants among them using Computed Tomography (CT) and Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). These are the best modalities of choice for imaging the transverse process because it has a capability of displaying both bone and soft tissue and it is used as a diagnostic tool for identifying the anatomical variants of the transverse process and its anatomical changes. It is used as a pre-operative map to guide the respective physicians for further surgeries or for any other procedures. Hence, the knowledge about the variation in transverse and its Castellvi classification types will help to perform the neural or vascular examination easily or else it may result in some complication during investigation of these structures. As a result, this study will provide a guidance to surgeons in predicting and minimizing the intraoperative complications.

METHODS:

This retrospective study was conducted at A.J. Hospital and Research Centre, Mangalore. This study was performed between September 2023 to June 2024. Among the patients referred to Department of Radio-Diagnosis and Imaging. All the patient with the age ranging from 20 to 80 years with irrespective of gender were considered. This study includes 873.4 \approx 874 patients who undergone CT Lumbar Spine and Abdomen scan with a standardized protocol performed in Siemens Somatom go. Top Dual Energy 128 Slice CT Scanner. Then the images obtained are reconstructed and were analysed on Syngo-via workstations. And in MRI the patient undergone lumbar spine scan with a standard protocol in MAGNETOM AVANTO 1.5Tesla SIEMENS MRI. In this study the acquired images were evaluated and noticed for the following variation in Transverse process of L5, patterns such as; Castellvi type I, type II, type III, type IV and its subtypes are: type Ia and Ib, type IIa and IIb, type IIIa and III b, and type IV, and normal variant are also included.

Finally, the transverse process status is noticed. Hence, these observations were tabulated and evaluated to classify the types of Castellvi classification in L5 and S1 vertebrae and to identify the most common variant among them and presented in the form of percentage values

RESULT:

In this study total 874 individuals were studied among them 502 males and 372 females with an age of 20 – 80 years. The prevalence of transverse sacralization of lumbosacral vertebrae turned out to

be 16.5% out of which Castellvi classification Type IIa was found most common turned out to be 5.4% in 47 patients. 22.7 comprised the group of normal variants (Castellvi classification type I) among type Ia was seen most common turned out to be 11.8% in 103 patients and 60.8% were normal having 531 patients.

CONCLUSION:

Conclusion This study intends the role of CT and MRI in the evaluation of anatomical variants of lumbar transverse process and their types of patterns through Castellvi classification to identify the LSTV as it affects the spinal movement and put excess stress on the lumbar vertebrae and in between discs. Moreover, it can have a bearing on counting of vertebral levels specially during planning of spinal surgery

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